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Title: The response to oxidative stress and metallomics analysis in a twin study: the role of the environment

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Keywords: antioxidant capacity; DNA repair; 8-oxoguanine DNA glycosylase; metals; twins

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Abstract: Inefficient response to oxidative stress has been associated with ageing and health risk. Metals are known to inhibit DNA repair and may modify the antioxidant response. How genetic variability and lifestyle factors modulate the response to oxidative stress is poorly explored. Our study aims to disentangle the contribution of genetics and environmental exposures to oxidative stress response using data from twin pairs. The non-enzymatic antioxidant capacity (NEAC), the repair capacity of 8-oxo-7,8-dihydroguanine (OGG activity) and the levels of twelve metals were measured in blood of 64 monozygotic and 31 dizygotic twin pairs. The contributions of genetic and environmental effects were assessed using standard univariate twin modelling. NEAC and OGG activity significantly decreased with age. Gender-, age- and body mass index-associated differences were identified for some metals. Principal Component Analysis identified two groups of metals whose levels in blood were highly correlated: As, Hg, Pb, Se, Zn and Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni. The environmental influence was predominant on OGG activity and NEAC variance whereas for most metals the best-fitting model incorporated additive genetic and unique environmental sources of variance. NEAC and OGG activity were both inversely correlated with blood levels of various metals. The inhibition of OGG activity by Cd was largely explained by smoking.

Our data show a substantial role of environmental factors in NEAC and OGG activity variance that is not explained by twins' age. Exogenous environmental factors such as metals contribute to oxidative stress by decreasing NEAC and inhibiting repair of oxidatively-induced DNA damage

Dear Editor,

The few editing issues indicated by the reviewer have been corrected.
We hope that in this revised version our MS is acceptable for publication in FRBM.

Yours Sincerely,

Eugenia Dogliotti

Answer to reviewer

The editing issues have been corrected as specified below. Thank you for your careful reading of our MS:

Reviewers' comments:

Reviewer #1: The requested clarifications have been adequately provided by the authors making the novel version of the manuscript worthy of publication in the Journal. There are, however, a few minor editing issues (see below) that still need appropriate correction.

Pg 9, ln 8: "oxidized ..." should be "oxidised ..." in order to be consistent with the preferential use of the English language (UK) in the manuscript; see also pg 16, first line.

[These words have been corrected as requested](#)

Pg 11, ln 15: "variation ..." or "variations ..."?

Pg 12, ln 8: "relation ..." or "relations ..."?

Pg 12, ln 9: "correlation ..." or "correlations ..."?

[In all these cases we believe that the singular is more appropriate](#)

Pg 14, ln 3: "normalization ..." should be "normalisation ...".

[This word has been corrected as requested](#)

Highlights

The key factors in the response to oxidative stress are identified by a twin study

DNA repair and antioxidant capacity are largely influenced by environment

Metals contribute to oxidative stress by inhibiting DNA repair and antioxidant capacity

The response to oxidative stress and metallomics analysis in a twin study: the role of the environment

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Running title: Oxidative stress and metals in twins

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Abstract

Inefficient response to oxidative stress has been associated with ageing and health risk. Metals are known to inhibit DNA repair and may modify the antioxidant response. How genetic variability and lifestyle factors modulate the response to oxidative stress is poorly explored. Our study aims to disentangle the contribution of genetics and environmental exposures to oxidative stress response using data from twin pairs. The non-enzymatic antioxidant capacity (NEAC), the repair capacity of 8-oxo-7,8-dihydroguanine (OGG activity) and the levels of twelve metals were measured in blood of 64 monozygotic and 31 dizygotic twin pairs. The contributions of genetic and environmental effects were assessed using standard univariate twin modelling. NEAC and OGG activity significantly decreased with age. Gender-, age- and body mass index-associated differences were identified for some metals. Principal Component Analysis identified two groups of metals whose levels in blood were highly correlated: As, Hg, Pb, Se, Zn and Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni. The environmental influence was predominant on OGG activity and NEAC variance whereas for most metals the best-fitting model incorporated additive genetic and unique environmental sources of variance. NEAC and OGG activity were both inversely correlated with blood levels of various metals. The inhibition of OGG activity by Cd was largely explained by smoking.

Our data show a substantial role of environmental factors in NEAC and OGG activity variance that is not explained by twins' age. Exogenous environmental factors such as metals contribute to oxidative stress by decreasing NEAC and inhibiting repair of oxidatively-induced DNA damage

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Introduction

Reactive oxygen radicals (ROS) are produced in the body, primarily as a result of aerobic metabolism, and are involved in many vital cell activities such as signal transduction and gene transcription therefore playing beneficial effects on the organisms. Antioxidants defence systems co-evolved along with aerobic metabolism to counteract oxidative damage (reviewed in 1). Antioxidants, such as glutathione and vitamins, together with antioxidant enzymes, such as superoxide dismutases, catalases and glutathione peroxidases, help to regulate the endogenous ROS. The maintenance of the redox balance is mostly seen as a genetic trait with the transcription factor Nrf2 as master regulator of the antioxidant response modulating the expression of hundreds of genes (reviewed in 2). These latter include not only the familiar antioxidant enzymes, but also genes involved in the immune and inflammatory responses, tissue remodelling, carcinogenesis, and cognitive dysfunction. However, humans are constantly exposed to ROS from environmental sources such as pollutants and cigarette smoke that may act independently and concomitantly of genetic factors. Among these environmental threats, metals are an important category that present as unifying factor, in determining their toxicity, the generation of ROS and nitrogen species (reviewed in 3-4). Metals may impact on the redox status either by undergoing redox-cycling reactions or by depletion of major antioxidants-and bonding to sulfhydryl groups of proteins. Moreover, environmental factors can induce the release of harmful “free” metals from storage proteins thus initiating ROS-producing reactions (5, 6). Alterations in metal homeostasis have been suggested as a key factor in the development of several disorders including neurological diseases (7). Exposure to metals may also impact on metabolism (8), such as by substituting for essential micronutrients and for other metals, or by inducing oxidative stress (9). When the overproduction of ROS exceeds the cell defence mechanisms, free radicals and singlet oxygen may damage DNA, RNA and proteins. The control of genomic stability is of

utmost importance for the organism and cells are endowed of DNA repair mechanisms that maintain a low level of oxidatively-induced DNA damage. Among these mechanisms the base excision repair (BER) is the most relevant and within BER the 8-oxoguanine DNA glycosylase, OGG1, is the primary enzyme responsible for the excision of 8-oxo-7,8-dihydroguanine (8-oxoGua), a mutagenic base that occurs as a result of exposure to the hydroxyl radical (*OH), singlet oxygen (¹O₂) and one-electron oxidants (10). Several studies indicate that OGG1 activity is highly sensitive to inactivation by oxidizing agents (11-12). Toxic metal ions may also interfere with DNA repair processes by inactivating the enzyme(s) directly, for example by reaction with histidine or cysteine residues, or by competing with and displacing essential metal ions (reviewed in 13). Recent studies indicate that the inhibition of DNA repair by metals may also influence the choice of the DNA repair pathway thus favouring “error-prone” mechanisms (14). By interference with cellular redox regulation, inhibition of DNA repair and/or deregulation of cell proliferation metals may induce genetic instability and possibly carcinogenic effects (reviewed in 15).

Twin studies have been widely used to estimate the heritability of complex traits and, more recently, to quantify the contributions that genes, the shared environment, the individual-specific environment and their interactions make to human complex traits (16). The comparison of the similarity between pairs of identical twins (monozygotic, MZ) and fraternal twins (dizygotic, DZ) allows to measure the contribution of genetics, as opposed to environment, to a given trait or condition of interest (17).

In this study we have addressed the question of the relative contribution of genetic and environmental factors to the body’s redox homeostasis by analysing in blood samples from MZ and DZ pairs the non-enzymatic antioxidant activity (NEAC), as a biomarker of in vivo antioxidant status (18), and OGG activity, as a biomarker of oxidatively-induced DNA damage repair (19), together with a descriptor of metal burden, i.e. metallomics of blood (20).

This study has revealed the importance of environmental factors in the control of the redox balance.

Materials and Methods (see also Supplemental Material)

Study subjects. Same sex twin pairs were selected from the Italian Twin Registry (21) aged over 18 and a final number of 190 twins were characterized (Figure S1). Sixty ml of blood were drawn from each subject in lithium heparin, EDTA or serum separator tubes, 5 ml were frozen at -20°C for metal determination, and the remaining volume was immediately processed to obtain lymphocytes and plasma and stored as required.

Metallomics analysis. One ml of blood was microwave digested (ETHOS-Mega II oven, FKV, Bergamo, Italy) in 15-ml plastic tubes (Falcon, Becton, Franklin Lakes, NJ) with the addition of 2 ml of suprapur concentrated HNO₃ (Romil Ltd, Cambridge, UK). Aluminium (Al), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), mercury (Hg), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), selenium (Se), and zinc (Zn) were measured by sector field inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SF-ICP-MS) (ThermoFischer, Bremen, Germany) as previously reported (22-24).

NEAC assay. Plasma was obtained from venous blood collected into lithium heparin vacuum tubes, centrifuged at 1500 rcf for 15 min and stored at -80°C prior to assay. NEAC in plasma samples was determined in 116 twins using a spectrophotometric assay based on the reduction of Cu⁺⁺ to Cu⁺ by the activity of all non enzymatic reducing species present in the sample (25).

OGG assay. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) were separated by centrifugation with Ficoll Paque PLUS (GE Healthcare, Milan, Italy) from heparinised venous blood and stored in liquid nitrogen. OGG activity was measured in protein extracts from PBMC by using as substrate a 6-carboxyfluorescein (6-FAM) 3'end-labelled 30 base pairs duplex containing a single 8-oxoGua (26).

Statistical analysis. Subjects were analysed both as individuals and as twin pairs. Descriptive analysis (mean± standard deviation for continuous variables, percentage for

categorical variables) for investigated characteristics was conducted using Stata Software (version 11.2, StataCorp, College Station, TX). Robust regression was used to identify variables associated with NEAC or OGG activity taking into account the dependence of twin data within pairs. Twin analyses were conducted using standard univariate twin modelling based on linear structural equations (17).

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on blood metal data to study the relationships among measured levels of different metals and to single out, if any, common sources (27).

A mediation analysis was performed to estimate the relationship of blood Cd levels to smoke habits and OGG activity. Mediation was evaluated by multiple regression (28).

Results

Study population. Characteristics of the study population are presented in Table S1. The 190 Italian twins included 64 monozygotic (MZ) and 31 dizygotic (DZ) pairs. There were no significant differences between MZ and DZ twins for demographic, clinical and biochemical characteristics. MZ and DZ twins were also similar regarding the smoking habits. This population was analysed for blood metal levels, OGG activity and NEAC.

Metallomics, NEAC and OGG activity profile in the twin population. In searching for environmental factors that could impact on oxidative stress response, chronic metal burden in blood was measured by SF-ICP-MS in the twin population (Table 1). The blood metal levels are within the range of the reference values obtained in Italian human biomonitoring surveys conducted on healthy adult subjects (18-65 years) (29-30). To test whether there are correlations between the concentrations of different elements, PCA was conducted to identify groups of interrelated variables (Principal Components, PCs). The first five PCs accounted for 65% of the metal total variation (Table 2) suggesting that the original variables were not highly correlated. The remaining seven PCs accounted for little variation (about 35%) and could be ignored being largely inside the noise floor (31). PC1 explained 22% of the total variation and all metals, but Al, Co and Cr, had positive correlation on PC1. As shown in Table 2, positive correlations on PC1, with As, Hg, Pb, Se and Zn as major contributors in variation, were higher than 0.63. PC2 explained 14% of the total variation. The variables mostly loaded on PC2 are Al, Co, Cr, Mn and Ni (range: 0.45-0.57 for Mn and Co, respectively). This implies that As, Hg, Pb, Se and Zn share common genetic/environmental factors that differ from those shared by Al, Co, Cr, Mn and Ni. Cd showed a positive correlation on both PC1 and PC2 (0.41 and 0.40 respectively). The third component explained about 12% of the variation among samples and was mainly related to Cr and Ni (positive correlation) and with Mn (negative correlation).

Plasma levels of NEAC are considered good indicators of in vivo antioxidant status as they are the result of the cumulative action of all the antioxidant molecules and of their synergic interactions. In our twin population NEAC had a normal distribution with a mean value of 1981 $\mu\text{moles/L}$ and a standard deviation of 397 $\mu\text{moles/L}$ of reducing power (Figure 1A).

The OGG assay measures the specific activity of the enzyme(s) that remove 8-oxoGua from DNA in protein extracts. This assay predominantly measures the activity of OGG1 that is the major eukaryotic enzyme that cleaves this oxidised base. An inter-individual variation of almost 5-fold in OGG activity is observed, with a mean activity of 1.3 fmoles/ μg cell extract (Figure 1B).

As shown in Table 3, age is associated with increased blood levels of most metals (e.g. As, Cd, Co, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Se, Zn). Gender had a specific effect on the levels of several metals being Cd, Co, Cu and Mn higher in females and As, Pb, Se and Zn higher in males. In addition in women a negative correlation between serum ferritin and Cd blood levels ($r=-0.10$, $P=0.30$) was observed. Smoke habits were associated with increased levels of Cd and decreased levels of Mn. Significant differences between body mass index (BMI) classes ($<25\text{kg/m}^2$ vs $\geq 25\text{kg/m}^2$) were identified with regard to As, Ni, Pb, Se and Zn.

As shown in Table 4, NEAC and OGG activity were inversely and significantly associated with age and were not affected by gender, zygosity and BMI ($P>0.05$). Taking into account age effect, smoke habits were significantly associated with decreased OGG activity (adjusted β coefficient= -0.11, $p=0.04$).

The effects of metals on NEAC and OGG activity. When the association between metal blood levels and NEAC or OGG activity was addressed (Table 5), a significant inverse association was observed between NEAC and Pb (β coefficient= -6.95; $p=0.03$) and between OGG activity and Al (β coefficient= -0.007; $p=0.04$), Cd (β coefficient=-0.16; $p=0.009$), Mn

(β coefficient= -0.03, $p=0.008$) and Ni (β coefficient= -0.024; $p=0.046$). Furthermore, NEAC and OGG activity were both significantly associated with the second principal component.

The association between Cd and OGG activity was further investigated. Since the median whole blood Cd content in smokers (0.89 $\mu\text{g/L}$) was almost 2-fold that in non-smokers (0.53 $\mu\text{g/L}$) (Table 3) and current smoking habits predict Cd and OGG activity (β coefficient=0.42; $p<0.001$; β coefficient = -0.11; $p=0.04$, respectively), we hypothesised that Cd may play a mediation role in the process by which cigarette smoking affects OGG activity. We observed that the effect of Cd (mediator variable) on OGG activity was still present after controlling for smoke although β coefficient does not reach significance (β coefficient= -0.12; $P=0.11$). The smoking habits do not account for the decrease of OGG activity by Mn, that is the other metal besides Cd associated with smoking (Table 5), on OGG activity.

Heritability estimates. Substantial influence from genetic factors on a trait is detectable as a greater MZ compared to DZ similarity. NEAC levels showed a low within-pair correlations in both zygosity groups (MZ=0.06 95%CI: -0.01, 0.13; DZ=0.19 95%CI: 0.10, 0.27) while OGG activity showed high within-pair correlations in both groups (MZ=0.73, 95% CI:0.55, 0.84; DZ=0.70, 95%CI:0.32, 0.86). Furthermore no strong differences between correlations in MZ and DZ were observed, suggesting the presence of weak genetic influences.

The results of twin modelling, adjusted by age and gender, indicate that only environmental factors contributed to total variance of NEAC as well as of OGG activity (Table 6). Interestingly, in the case of NEAC the unshared environment ($E=0.77$) played a dominant role while in the case of OGG activity the shared environment was the main contributor ($C=0.72$).

The results of univariate twin modelling on metal blood levels are shown in Table 6. The best-fitting model was an AE model incorporating additive genetic and unique environmental sources of variation for the following metals: Al, As, Cd, Co, Cu, Hg, Mn, Ni, Zn. The estimations of genetic components (A) ranged from 0.15 (As) to 0.79 (Zn). For Cr the best explanation of the data was obtained under a model (E model) in which the inter-individual variance was entirely due to environmental factors not shared by the twins. With respect to Pb and Se concentration, the best-fitting model was a CE model and the estimates of these unique environmental effects were 0.56 and 0.40, respectively.

Discussion

This is the first study to investigate the metal profile concomitantly to biomarkers of susceptibility to oxidative stress (i.e. antioxidant response and DNA repair capacity) in a twin population in order to disentangle the genetic and environmental factors responsible for the maintenance of the redox status.

Gender, age and BMI differences as a function of metal blood levels. The accumulation and body burden of toxic elements are expected to be affected by variation in exposure as well as by genetic variability in absorption and distribution. The blood metallomics profile of our twins confirms the role of gender and age among the determinants of blood concentration for some metals. For instance, in the case of Cd, women presented higher blood levels than men and a negative correlation with serum ferritin was observed confirming that body iron stores affect Cd absorption (32-33). Conversely, blood Pb levels were higher in males than in women as expected from the higher hematocrit levels of men. Blood levels of several metals i.e. As, Cd, Cu, Ni, Pb, Se and Zn were positively correlated

with age indicating that age-related changes in metabolism may impact on metal body burden (8).

As, Pb, Ni, Se and Zn blood levels were significantly associated with BMI \geq 25. Several reports describe an association between high heavy metals in blood and insulin resistance and/or metabolic syndrome. In particular, As and Pb have been shown to be risk factors for developing diabetes and obesity (34-35).

In our study PCA revealed associations between the levels of several of the metals investigated. For instance, As, Hg, Pb, Se, and Zn showed positive relation with the first component and Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni showed positive correlation with the second component. It might be possible that the correlations within PC are due to the same environmental factors (e.g. diet, common adverse environment) but the influence of genetic effects cannot be excluded. Indeed in the large twin population analysed by Whitfield and coworkers (36), similarly to our study a substantial association between As, Hg and Se and Zn was reported, and As and Hg were shown to correlate mainly due to genetic effects.

Impact of metals on NEAC and OGG activity. In this study we investigated redox-active metals such as As, Mn, Cu and Cr that undergo redox cycling as well as redox-inactive metals such as Pb, Cd, Hg that act indirectly by depleting the major cellular antioxidants. Either type of metals may cause an increase in production of ROS. The tolerance to ROS-mediated metal toxicity is determined by the variation in antioxidant status and repair capacity. In this study we identify some metals that strongly affect these cell defenses.

NEAC is a sensitive and reliable marker to detect changes of in vivo oxidative stress (37). We show that plasma Pb levels are inversely correlated with NEAC, likely reflecting its capacity to inhibit antioxidant enzymes (reviewed in 38). Pb shares with other metals this mechanism, thus it should be extremely effective in altering the body antioxidant status to be specifically

identified in our screening. It is of note that a unique feature of Pb is the lack of a threshold level for its neurotoxicity (35) indicating the highly toxic nature of this metal.

On the other hand the blood levels of other metals, namely Al, Cd, Mn and Ni, correlate with OGG activity indicating that DNA repair proteins can also be a target of toxic metals. Cd and Ni inhibit several types of DNA repair and, in the case of oxidatively-induced DNA damage repair, they are extremely effective at doses which do not generate detectable damage (39). In particular, Cd has been reported to effectively inhibit OGG1 by reacting with –SH groups of critical residues (11-12) and by suppression of OGG1 transcription (40). Al ions inhibit oxidatively-induced DNA damage repair (41) and inhibition of OGG1 activity by Mn has been observed in neuronal cells (42) that are highly vulnerable to oxidative stress upon chronic poisoning (43).

As stated above, the inhibition of DNA repair is a common feature of several metals so the question remains why Al, Mn, Ni and Cd levels are specifically and inversely associated with OGG activity. It is of note that Al, Mn and Ni belong to the group of metals that associate with the second component in the PCA, suggesting that they might share common environmental sources. Diet is the major route of exposure for all these metals, with the exception of Cd, where smoking prevails. A detailed questionnaire on diet habits was collected for all participants and further studies will address this topic. Several studies report a dramatic difference in serum/blood cadmium levels between smokers and non-smokers at a young age (3-fold increase), and a lower but still significant difference at older ages (approximately 2-fold increase) (44). This increase is confirmed in our study that shows 2-fold increase in Cd blood levels in smokers as compared to ex-or no-smokers. We observed that the association of smoking habits with OGG activity is greatly reduced and not significant when Cd levels are taken into account, suggesting a role for this metal in the mediation of the effects of smoke on OGG activity. It is of note that both the blood Cd levels

as well as OGG activity revert to normal in the category of the ex-smokers. This is in line with in vitro observations that, following acute exposure of human cells to Cd, excretion of the metal leads to normalisation of the redox cell status and restoration of an active OGG1 (11). OGG activity has been shown to be a predictive biomarker of lung cancer (45). In the study by Paz-Elizur et al. (45) a cumulative effect of low OGG activity and smoking was reported indicating that smoking increases the risk of mutation load (that may determine progress to cancer) not only via OGG1-mediated mechanisms. Mouse and human cell lines lacking OGG1 show increased steady state levels of 8-oxoGua in their genome (46). Also cell lines that are not fully deprived of OGG1 but present decreased OGG1 activity due to partially inactivating polymorphisms (i.e. Ser326Cys) show slower repair of oxidatively-induced guanine modifications in vivo (47). The reduction in OGG1 activity that we observe in our study in association with increased blood levels of some metals is unlikely to give rise to permanent alteration of the steady state level of 8-oxoGua but more likely to transitory changes associated with the persistence of the toxic metal.

Age-related decrease in both the NEAC and OGG activity were detected in our study indicating that the decline in the antioxidant capacity (48) together with that in the repair of oxidatively-induced DNA damage (19) may play an important role in age-related accumulation of cell damage by ROS.

Heritability estimates: the environmental factors prevail. The best-fitting biometric models indicated that environmental factors are the major contributors to inter-individual differences in metal levels (with some exceptions) as well as in NEAC and OGG activity.

Environmental exposures were also shown to govern the accumulation of metals, with some contribution by genetic factors, in a large adult twin population (36). In our study it is of note the contribution of genetic variance in the case of Mn and Zn which are all essential trace elements. It should be mentioned that in the case of Pb and Se significant shared

environmental influences were identified. Environmental effects shared within twin pairs reflect non heritable phenomena occurring during intrauterine life and/or the early postnatal period (e.g. maternal diet, gestational infections or chemical exposures during pregnancy). Pb passes the placenta and Pb-mediated epigenetic mechanisms in the foetus are dramatically associated with impaired brain development (49). Whether epigenetic mechanisms early in life might determine Pb body burden in adults should be investigated in larger studies.

The inter-individual differences in NEAC levels were mostly determined by the non-shared environmental component whereas the OGG capacity was accounted by both shared and non-shared environmental factors. This might account for the low within-pair correlations in MZ and DZ twin groups in the case of NAEC as compared to the high within-pair correlations in both zygosity groups in the case of OGG activity. In line with the idea of an environmental factors-driven antioxidant capacity, a study on elderly Danish twins (50) has shown that urinary markers of oxidative stress, measuring oxidatively-induced damage to nucleic acids and lipids, are predominantly determined by non genetic factors. Although epigenetic changes have been proposed in the link between oxidative stress levels and birth weight in twin neonates (51) and risk of complex diseases later in life (52) whether the shared environmental effects in the case of OGG activity are part of a “signature” by oxidative stress at birth on DNA repair capacity is presently very speculative.

The lack of genetic factors in determining DNA repair capacity was somewhat surprisingly. Previous studies have suggested that radiation-induced micronucleus frequency (reviewed in 53), mutagenic sensitivity to a variety of DNA damaging agents (54), and apoptotic (55) and cell-cycle (56) response to ionizing radiation are highly heritable. However, no effect of the genetic background was observed when baseline and radiation-induced DNA single strand breaks (SSB) were examined (57). The human DNA repair proteome is susceptible to oxidation (58) and BER enzymes might be especially sensitive thus

accounting for the environmental component when the repair of oxidised DNA bases or SSB is measured. In the study by Garm et al. (57) it was shown that SSB repair induced by γ -rays is accounted for by individual specific environmental exposures whereas the basal levels of endogenous SSB, γ -H2AX response and double strand break repair capacity can be accounted for by both common and non-shared environmental factors. Similarly, the shared environmental component prevails in the case of basal OGG activity. Birth is associated with a burst of oxidative stress (59) that might impact on the capacity to repair DNA damage later in life. Further studies are required to address this topic.

Conclusions

Genetic background may be critical for disease development, but environmental factors may have a dominant role in disease progression. This study provides clear evidence that it is the exposure to toxic elements in the environment that governs our capacity to respond to oxidative stress. Genetic factors play a minor role. Toxic metals, that may contaminate air, water, soil and food, are identified as important contributors via induction of oxidative stress. Our findings implicate that the prevention of adverse environments/life style habits is an effective measure to limit the deleterious health effects of excessive oxidatively-induced damage.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare they have no actual or potential competing financial interests.

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Table 1. Blood metal levels in twins as compared to reference values from Italian surveys conducted on healthy adult subjects

	This study		Reference values	
	Median (mean ^a)	5 th -95 th percentiles	Median (mean ^a)	5 th -95 th percentiles
Al	12.10 (13.25)	4.22-28.13	15.3 (17.0) ²	5.93-33.3
As	1.71 (2.34)	0.36-5.80	1.16 (1.14) ¹	0.28-5.32
Cd	0.60 (0.73)	0.23-1.70	0.52 (0.63) ¹	0.23-1.42
Co	0.10 (0.13)	0.03-0.34	0.14 (0.19) ¹	0.05-0.44
Cr	0.18 (0.39)	0.02-1.52	0.23 (0.38) ¹	0.06-1.09
Cu	919.0 (955)	739.7-1322.5	935 (938) ²	686-1157
Hg	1.72 (2.29)	0.36-6.80	1.15 (1.68) ¹	0.35-5.16
Mn	8.45 (8.69)	4.62-13.37	8.30 (8.74) ¹	4.41-14.5
Ni	0.52 (1.15)	0.10-4.56	0.90 (1.23) ¹	0.35-2.62
Pb	17.87 (23.58)	9.97-57.20	20.2 (24.0) ¹	7.38-51.7
Se	98.39 (102.24)	60.43-156.38	- (91.3) ³	-
Zn	5920.6 (6043)	4560.7-7940.3	6597 (6717) ²	5189-8337

Blood samples from 173 twins were analysed. Values are expressed as µg/L

^a arithmetic mean;

¹ Alimonti et al. (29); ² Alimonti et al. (60); ³ Alimonti et al. (30).

Table 2: Proportion of variability and contribution of metals to the five principal components (PC)

Statistical parameters	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5
Variance (%)	22	14	12	9	8
Cumulative Variance	0.22	0.36	0.48	0.57	0.65
Al	-0.002	0.531	0.0004	-0.091	-0.651
As	0.663	0.024	0.205	-0.254	0.293
Cd	0.406	0.397	0.008	-0.074	-0.357
Co	-0.121	0.572	-0.247	-0.513	0.356
Cr	-0.184	0.521	0.605	0.031	0.092
Cu	0.068	0.383	-0.461	0.573	0.254
Hg	0.636	-0.111	0.082	-0.402	0.122
Mn	0.233	0.448	-0.647	-0.057	0.059
Ni	0.036	0.515	0.568	0.295	0.231
Pb	0.689	0.004	0.070	-0.034	-0.158
Se	0.764	-0.101	-0.014	0.233	-0.015
Zn	0.696	-0.021	0.019	0.297	0.018

The numbers in the columns are factor loadings that represent the correlations between metals and principal components.

Table 3. Differences in metal blood levels by twin characteristics

	Al	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Hg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Se	Zn
Age at enrollment												
≤40	12.84	1.22	0.51	0.11	0.20	884.61	1.50	8.34	0.31	14.00	83.02	5334.79
>40	11.43	2.57	0.70	0.08	0.17	937.83	1.92	8.49	0.95	25.13	112.61	6617.55
		P<0.001	P<0.001	P=0.007		P=0.009	P=0.002		P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001
Gender												
Male	11.45	2.62	0.53	0.08	0.18	867.95	1.78	7.30	0.71	25.04	109.16	6703.98
Female	12.35	1.37	0.69	0.12	0.19	955.35	1.66	8.66	0.46	15.72	94.98	5682.49
		P=0.003	P=0.001	P<0.001		P<0.001		P<0.001		P<0.001	P=0.004	P<0.001
Smoking habits												
Never–ex smokers	11.43	1.71	0.53	0.10	0.18	921.30	1.58	8.67	0.51	18.17	101.32	6020.75
Current smokers	13.39	1.80	0.89	0.12	0.18	902.09	1.92	7.56	0.55	17.88	92.79	5696.25
			P<0.001					P=0.009				
BMI												
<25	11.34	1.32	0.58	0.11	0.24	919.86	1.72	8.29	0.38	15.52	91.94	5614.26
≥25	12.11	2.55	0.63	0.10	0.15	918.68	1.69	8.47	0.84	23.39	105.94	6630.21
		P=0.001							P=0.002	P<0.001	P=0.002	P<0.001

The reported values are medians expressed as µg/L.

P values were obtained by Mann-Whitney U-test; only significant differences are reported.

Table 4. Association between NEAC or OGG activity and characteristics of twins

	NEAC						OGG activity					
	N	Mean \pm SD	β Coefficient	P	β Coefficient age adjusted	P _{adj}	N	Mean \pm SD	β Coefficient	P	β Coefficient age adjusted	P _{adj}
Age at enrollment												
≤ 40	50	2200.7 \pm 368.7					44	1.44 \pm 0.38				
>40	66	1814.7 \pm 333.0	-386.0	<0.01	-	-	62	1.21 \pm 0.38	-0.23	0.02	-	-
Gender												
Male	44	1982.8 \pm 427.2					44	1.30 \pm 0.37				
Female	72	1980.1 \pm 380.4	-2.72	0.98	-54.87	0.50	62	1.31 \pm 0.41	0.0005	1.0	-0.028	0.78
Smoking habits												
Never-ex smokers	87	1978.8 \pm 386.4					78	1.33 \pm 0.42				
Current smokers	27	1971.4 \pm 439.8	-12.97	0.89	-23.48	0.78	26	1.23 \pm 0.31	-0.11	0.05	-0.11	0.04
Zygoty												
MZ	84	1953.1 \pm 359.9					74	1.33 \pm 0.41				
DZ	32	2054.5 \pm 479.5	101.4	0.36	63.48	0.52	32	1.24 \pm 0.34	-0.09	0.39	-0.12	0.21
BMI												
<25	61	2025.4 \pm 388.2					55	1.31 \pm 0.43				
25-30	40	1942.2 \pm 414.4	-59.3	0.43	26.7	0.69	39	1.29 \pm 0.37	-0.03	0.62	-0.007	0.91
≥ 30	15	1904.4 \pm 388.1	-95.9	0.39	51.4	0.66	12	1.33 \pm 0.33	0.07	0.44	0.11	0.26

β coefficient is defined as the rate of change of the dependent variable (Y) for a unit change in the predictor variable (X). Age adjusted β coefficient is also displayed

SD=Standard Deviation; MZ: Monozygotic twins; DZ=Dizygotic twins; BMI= Body mass index (kg/m²)

Table 5. Regression coefficients, age adjusted, of metal blood levels and NEAC or OGG activity

	NEAC		OGG activity	
	β coefficient	P	β coefficient	P
Al	-3.28	0.57	-0.007	0.04
As	12.53	0.52	-0.012	0.26
Cd	-145.95	0.14	-0.162	0.009
Co	-620.9	0.06	-0.647	0.11
Cr	-5.80	0.94	0.002	0.98
Cu	-0.37	0.06	0.00002	0.93
Hg	4.56	0.73	-0.021	0.16
Mn	-19.92	0.07	-0.03	0.008
Ni	-19.53	0.43	-0.024	0.046
Pb	-6.95	0.03	0.003	0.21
Se	-0.48	0.72	0.0003	0.85
Zn	-0.02	0.63	0	0.85

Analysis for metal levels and NEAC or OGG activity were available on 103 and 96 twins respectively

Table 6. Standardized genetic and environmental variance components of NEAC, OGG activity and metal concentrations as estimated from the best-fitting structural equation models.

	Twins	Standardized variance components		
		A (95% CI)	C (95% CI)	E (95% CI)
NEAC	116	-	0.23 (0, 0.46)	0.77 (0.54, 1.00)
OGG activity	106	-	0.72 (0.57, 0.83)	0.28 (0.17, 0.43)
Al	170	0.17 (0, 0.39)	-	0.83 (0.61, 1.0)
As	170	0.15 (0, 0.39)	-	0.85 (0.61, 1.0)
Cd	170	0.36 (0.14, 0.55)	-	0.64 (0.45, 0.86)
Co	170	0.55 (0.32, 0.71)	-	0.45 (0.29, 0.68)
Cr	170	-	-	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Cu	170	0.21 (0, 0.41)	-	0.79 (0.59, 1.0)
Hg	170	0.33 (0.10, 0.53)	-	0.67 (0.47, 0.91)
Mn	170	0.69 (0.54, 0.79)	-	0.31 (0.21, 0.46)
Ni	170	0.32 (0.02, 0.56)	-	0.68 (0.44, 0.98)
Pb	170	-	0.44 (0.25, 0.59)	0.56 (0.41, 0.75)
Se	170	-	0.60 (0.45, 0.72)	0.40 (0.28, 0.55)
Zn	170	0.79 (0.67, 0.87)	-	0.21 (0.13, 0.33)

A, additive genetic variance; C, shared environmental variance; E, unique environmental variance. Covariates: age and gender. Numbers in parentheses indicate 95% confidence intervals.

The response to oxidative stress and metallomics analysis in a twin study: the role of the environment

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Abstract

Inefficient response to oxidative stress has been associated with ageing and health risk. Metals are known to inhibit DNA repair and may modify the antioxidant response. How genetic variability and lifestyle factors modulate the response to oxidative stress is poorly explored. Our study aims to disentangle the contribution of genetics and environmental exposures to oxidative stress response using data from twin pairs. The non-enzymatic antioxidant capacity (NEAC), the repair capacity of 8-oxo-7,8-dihydroguanine (OGG activity) and the levels of twelve metals were measured in blood of 64 monozygotic and 31 dizygotic twin pairs. The contributions of genetic and environmental effects were assessed using standard univariate twin modelling. NEAC and OGG activity significantly decreased with age. Gender-, age- and body mass index-associated differences were identified for some metals. Principal Component Analysis identified two groups of metals whose levels in blood were highly correlated: As, Hg, Pb, Se, Zn and Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni. The environmental influence was predominant on OGG activity and NEAC variance whereas for most metals the best-fitting model incorporated additive genetic and unique environmental sources of variance. NEAC and OGG activity were both inversely correlated with blood levels of various metals. The inhibition of OGG activity by Cd was largely explained by smoking.

Our data show a substantial role of environmental factors in NEAC and OGG activity variance that is not explained by twins' age. Exogenous environmental factors such as metals contribute to oxidative stress by decreasing NEAC and inhibiting repair of oxidatively-induced DNA damage

Key words: antioxidant capacity; DNA repair; 8-oxoguanine DNA glycosylase; metals; twins

Introduction

Reactive oxygen radicals (ROS) are produced in the body, primarily as a result of aerobic metabolism, and are involved in many vital cell activities such as signal transduction and gene transcription therefore playing beneficial effects on the organisms. Antioxidants defence systems co-evolved along with aerobic metabolism to counteract oxidative damage (reviewed in 1). Antioxidants, such as glutathione and vitamins, together with antioxidant enzymes, such as superoxide dismutases, catalases and glutathione peroxidases, help to regulate the endogenous ROS. The maintenance of the redox balance is mostly seen as a genetic trait with the transcription factor Nrf2 as master regulator of the antioxidant response modulating the expression of hundreds of genes (reviewed in 2). These latter include not only the familiar antioxidant enzymes, but also genes involved in the immune and inflammatory responses, tissue remodelling, carcinogenesis, and cognitive dysfunction. However, humans are constantly exposed to ROS from environmental sources such as pollutants and cigarette smoke that may act independently and concomitantly of genetic factors. Among these environmental threats, metals are an important category that present as unifying factor, in determining their toxicity, the generation of ROS and nitrogen species (reviewed in 3-4). Metals may impact on the redox status either by undergoing redox-cycling reactions or by depletion of major antioxidants-and bonding to sulfhydryl groups of proteins. Moreover, environmental factors can induce the release of harmful “free” metals from storage proteins thus initiating ROS-producing reactions (5, 6). Alterations in metal homeostasis have been suggested as a key factor in the development of several disorders including neurological diseases (7). Exposure to metals may also impact on metabolism (8), such as by substituting for essential micronutrients and for other metals, or by inducing oxidative stress (9). When the overproduction of ROS exceeds the cell defence mechanisms, free radicals and singlet oxygen may damage DNA, RNA and proteins. The control of genomic stability is of

utmost importance for the organism and cells are endowed of DNA repair mechanisms that maintain a low level of oxidatively-induced DNA damage. Among these mechanisms the base excision repair (BER) is the most relevant and within BER the 8-oxoguanine DNA glycosylase, OGG1, is the primary enzyme responsible for the excision of 8-oxo-7,8-dihydroguanine (8-oxoGua), a mutagenic base that occurs as a result of exposure to the hydroxyl radical (*OH), singlet oxygen (¹O₂) and one-electron oxidants (10). Several studies indicate that OGG1 activity is highly sensitive to inactivation by oxidizing agents (11-12). Toxic metal ions may also interfere with DNA repair processes by inactivating the enzyme(s) directly, for example by reaction with histidine or cysteine residues, or by competing with and displacing essential metal ions (reviewed in 13). Recent studies indicate that the inhibition of DNA repair by metals may also influence the choice of the DNA repair pathway thus favouring “error-prone” mechanisms (14). By interference with cellular redox regulation, inhibition of DNA repair and/or deregulation of cell proliferation metals may induce genetic instability and possibly carcinogenic effects (reviewed in 15).

Twin studies have been widely used to estimate the heritability of complex traits and, more recently, to quantify the contributions that genes, the shared environment, the individual-specific environment and their interactions make to human complex traits (16). The comparison of the similarity between pairs of identical twins (monozygotic, MZ) and fraternal twins (dizygotic, DZ) allows to measure the contribution of genetics, as opposed to environment, to a given trait or condition of interest (17).

In this study we have addressed the question of the relative contribution of genetic and environmental factors to the body’s redox homeostasis by analysing in blood samples from MZ and DZ pairs the non-enzymatic antioxidant activity (NEAC), as a biomarker of in vivo antioxidant status (18), and OGG activity, as a biomarker of oxidatively-induced DNA damage repair (19), together with a descriptor of metal burden, i.e. metallomics of blood (20).

This study has revealed the importance of environmental factors in the control of the redox balance.

Materials and Methods (see also Supplemental Material)

Study subjects. Same sex twin pairs were selected from the Italian Twin Registry (21) aged over 18 and a final number of 190 twins were characterized (Figure S1). Sixty ml of blood were drawn from each subject in lithium heparin, EDTA or serum separator tubes, 5 ml were frozen at -20°C for metal determination, and the remaining volume was immediately processed to obtain lymphocytes and plasma and stored as required.

Metallomics analysis. One ml of blood was microwave digested (ETHOS-Mega II oven, FKV, Bergamo, Italy) in 15-ml plastic tubes (Falcon, Becton, Franklin Lakes, NJ) with the addition of 2 ml of suprapur concentrated HNO₃ (Romil Ltd, Cambridge, UK). Aluminium (Al), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), mercury (Hg), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), selenium (Se), and zinc (Zn) were measured by sector field inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SF-ICP-MS) (ThermoFischer, Bremen, Germany) as previously reported (22-24).

NEAC assay. Plasma was obtained from venous blood collected into lithium heparin vacuum tubes, centrifuged at 1500 rcf for 15 min and stored at -80°C prior to assay. NEAC in plasma samples was determined in 116 twins using a spectrophotometric assay based on the reduction of Cu⁺⁺ to Cu⁺ by the activity of all non enzymatic reducing species present in the sample (25).

OGG assay. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) were separated by centrifugation with Ficoll Paque PLUS (GE Healthcare, Milan, Italy) from heparinised venous blood and stored in liquid nitrogen. OGG activity was measured in protein extracts from PBMC by using as substrate a 6-carboxyfluorescein (6-FAM) 3'end-labelled 30 base pairs duplex containing a single 8-oxoGua (26).

Statistical analysis. Subjects were analysed both as individuals and as twin pairs. Descriptive analysis (mean± standard deviation for continuous variables, percentage for

categorical variables) for investigated characteristics was conducted using Stata Software (version 11.2, StataCorp, College Station, TX). Robust regression was used to identify variables associated with NEAC or OGG activity taking into account the dependence of twin data within pairs. Twin analyses were conducted using standard univariate twin modelling based on linear structural equations (17).

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on blood metal data to study the relationships among measured levels of different metals and to single out, if any, common sources (27).

A mediation analysis was performed to estimate the relationship of blood Cd levels to smoke habits and OGG activity. Mediation was evaluated by multiple regression (28).

Results

Study population. Characteristics of the study population are presented in Table S1. The 190 Italian twins included 64 monozygotic (MZ) and 31 dizygotic (DZ) pairs. There were no significant differences between MZ and DZ twins for demographic, clinical and biochemical characteristics. MZ and DZ twins were also similar regarding the smoking habits. This population was analysed for blood metal levels, OGG activity and NEAC.

Metallomics, NEAC and OGG activity profile in the twin population. In searching for environmental factors that could impact on oxidative stress response, chronic metal burden in blood was measured by SF-ICP-MS in the twin population (Table 1). The blood metal levels are within the range of the reference values obtained in Italian human biomonitoring surveys conducted on healthy adult subjects (18-65 years) (29-30). To test whether there are correlations between the concentrations of different elements, PCA was conducted to identify groups of interrelated variables (Principal Components, PCs). The first five PCs accounted for 65% of the metal total variation (Table 2) suggesting that the original variables were not highly correlated. The remaining seven PCs accounted for little variation (about 35%) and could be ignored being largely inside the noise floor (31). PC1 explained 22% of the total variation and all metals, but Al, Co and Cr, had positive correlation on PC1. As shown in Table 2, positive correlations on PC1, with As, Hg, Pb, Se and Zn as major contributors in variation, were higher than 0.63. PC2 explained 14% of the total variation. The variables mostly loaded on PC2 are Al, Co, Cr, Mn and Ni (range: 0.45-0.57 for Mn and Co, respectively). This implies that As, Hg, Pb, Se and Zn share common genetic/environmental factors that differ from those shared by Al, Co, Cr, Mn and Ni. Cd showed a positive correlation on both PC1 and PC2 (0.41 and 0.40 respectively). The third component explained about 12% of the variation among samples and was mainly related to Cr and Ni (positive correlation) and with Mn (negative correlation).

Plasma levels of NEAC are considered good indicators of in vivo antioxidant status as they are the result of the cumulative action of all the antioxidant molecules and of their synergic interactions. In our twin population NEAC had a normal distribution with a mean value of 1981 $\mu\text{moles/L}$ and a standard deviation of 397 $\mu\text{moles/L}$ of reducing power (Figure 1A).

The OGG assay measures the specific activity of the enzyme(s) that remove 8-oxoGua from DNA in protein extracts. This assay predominantly measures the activity of OGG1 that is the major eukaryotic enzyme that cleaves this oxidised base. An inter-individual variation of almost 5-fold in OGG activity is observed, with a mean activity of 1.3 fmoles/ μg cell extract (Figure 1B).

As shown in Table 3, age is associated with increased blood levels of most metals (e.g. As, Cd, Co, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Se, Zn). Gender had a specific effect on the levels of several metals being Cd, Co, Cu and Mn higher in females and As, Pb, Se and Zn higher in males. In addition in women a negative correlation between serum ferritin and Cd blood levels ($r=-0.10$, $P=0.30$) was observed. Smoke habits were associated with increased levels of Cd and decreased levels of Mn. Significant differences between body mass index (BMI) classes ($<25\text{kg/m}^2$ vs $\geq 25\text{kg/m}^2$) were identified with regard to As, Ni, Pb, Se and Zn.

As shown in Table 4, NEAC and OGG activity were inversely and significantly associated with age and were not affected by gender, zygosity and BMI ($P>0.05$). Taking into account age effect, smoke habits were significantly associated with decreased OGG activity (adjusted β coefficient= -0.11, $p=0.04$).

The effects of metals on NEAC and OGG activity. When the association between metal blood levels and NEAC or OGG activity was addressed (Table 5), a significant inverse association was observed between NEAC and Pb (β coefficient= -6.95; $p=0.03$) and between OGG activity and Al (β coefficient= -0.007; $p=0.04$), Cd (β coefficient=-0.16; $p=0.009$), Mn

(β coefficient= -0.03, $p=0.008$) and Ni (β coefficient= -0.024; $p=0.046$). Furthermore, NEAC and OGG activity were both significantly associated with the second principal component.

The association between Cd and OGG activity was further investigated. Since the median whole blood Cd content in smokers (0.89 $\mu\text{g/L}$) was almost 2-fold that in non-smokers (0.53 $\mu\text{g/L}$) (Table 3) and current smoking habits predict Cd and OGG activity (β coefficient=0.42; $p<0.001$; β coefficient = -0.11; $p=0.04$, respectively), we hypothesised that Cd may play a mediation role in the process by which cigarette smoking affects OGG activity. We observed that the effect of Cd (mediator variable) on OGG activity was still present after controlling for smoke although β coefficient does not reach significance (β coefficient= -0.12; $P=0.11$). The smoking habits do not account for the decrease of OGG activity by Mn, that is the other metal besides Cd associated with smoking (Table 5), on OGG activity.

Heritability estimates. Substantial influence from genetic factors on a trait is detectable as a greater MZ compared to DZ similarity. NEAC levels showed a low within-pair correlations in both zygosity groups (MZ=0.06 95%CI: -0.01, 0.13; DZ=0.19 95%CI: 0.10, 0.27) while OGG activity showed high within-pair correlations in both groups (MZ=0.73, 95% CI:0.55, 0.84; DZ=0.70, 95%CI:0.32, 0.86). Furthermore no strong differences between correlations in MZ and DZ were observed, suggesting the presence of weak genetic influences.

The results of twin modelling, adjusted by age and gender, indicate that only environmental factors contributed to total variance of NEAC as well as of OGG activity (Table 6). Interestingly, in the case of NEAC the unshared environment ($E=0.77$) played a dominant role while in the case of OGG activity the shared environment was the main contributor ($C=0.72$).

The results of univariate twin modelling on metal blood levels are shown in Table 6. The best-fitting model was an AE model incorporating additive genetic and unique environmental sources of variation for the following metals: Al, As, Cd, Co, Cu, Hg, Mn, Ni, Zn. The estimations of genetic components (A) ranged from 0.15 (As) to 0.79 (Zn). For Cr the best explanation of the data was obtained under a model (E model) in which the inter-individual variance was entirely due to environmental factors not shared by the twins. With respect to Pb and Se concentration, the best-fitting model was a CE model and the estimates of these unique environmental effects were 0.56 and 0.40, respectively.

Discussion

This is the first study to investigate the metal profile concomitantly to biomarkers of susceptibility to oxidative stress (i.e. antioxidant response and DNA repair capacity) in a twin population in order to disentangle the genetic and environmental factors responsible for the maintenance of the redox status.

Gender, age and BMI differences as a function of metal blood levels. The accumulation and body burden of toxic elements are expected to be affected by variation in exposure as well as by genetic variability in absorption and distribution. The blood metallomics profile of our twins confirms the role of gender and age among the determinants of blood concentration for some metals. For instance, in the case of Cd, women presented higher blood levels than men and a negative correlation with serum ferritin was observed confirming that body iron stores affect Cd absorption (32-33). Conversely, blood Pb levels were higher in males than in women as expected from the higher hematocrit levels of men. Blood levels of several metals i.e. As, Cd, Cu, Ni, Pb, Se and Zn were positively correlated

with age indicating that age-related changes in metabolism may impact on metal body burden (8).

As, Pb, Ni, Se and Zn blood levels were significantly associated with $BMI \geq 25$. Several reports describe an association between high heavy metals in blood and insulin resistance and/or metabolic syndrome. In particular, As and Pb have been shown to be risk factors for developing diabetes and obesity (34-35).

In our study PCA revealed associations between the levels of several of the metals investigated. For instance, As, Hg, Pb, Se, and Zn showed positive relation with the first component and Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni showed positive correlation with the second component. It might be possible that the correlations within PC are due to the same environmental factors (e.g. diet, common adverse environment) but the influence of genetic effects cannot be excluded. Indeed in the large twin population analysed by Whitfield and coworkers (36), similarly to our study a substantial association between As, Hg and Se and Zn was reported, and As and Hg were shown to correlate mainly due to genetic effects.

Impact of metals on NEAC and OGG activity. In this study we investigated redox-active metals such as As, Mn, Cu and Cr that undergo redox cycling as well as redox-inactive metals such as Pb, Cd, Hg that act indirectly by depleting the major cellular antioxidants. Either type of metals may cause an increase in production of ROS. The tolerance to ROS-mediated metal toxicity is determined by the variation in antioxidant status and repair capacity. In this study we identify some metals that strongly affect these cell defenses.

NEAC is a sensitive and reliable marker to detect changes of in vivo oxidative stress (37). We show that plasma Pb levels are inversely correlated with NEAC, likely reflecting its capacity to inhibit antioxidant enzymes (reviewed in 38). Pb shares with other metals this mechanism, thus it should be extremely effective in altering the body antioxidant status to be specifically

identified in our screening. It is of note that a unique feature of Pb is the lack of a threshold level for its neurotoxicity (35) indicating the highly toxic nature of this metal.

On the other hand the blood levels of other metals, namely Al, Cd, Mn and Ni, correlate with OGG activity indicating that DNA repair proteins can also be a target of toxic metals. Cd and Ni inhibit several types of DNA repair and, in the case of oxidatively-induced DNA damage repair, they are extremely effective at doses which do not generate detectable damage (39). In particular, Cd has been reported to effectively inhibit OGG1 by reacting with –SH groups of critical residues (11-12) and [by suppression of OGG1 transcription \(40\)](#). Al ions inhibit oxidatively-induced DNA damage repair (41) and inhibition of OGG1 activity by Mn has been observed in neuronal cells (42) that are highly vulnerable to oxidative stress upon chronic poisoning (43).

As stated above, the inhibition of DNA repair is a common feature of several metals so the question remains why Al, Mn, Ni and Cd levels are specifically and inversely associated with OGG activity. It is of note that Al, Mn and Ni belong to the group of metals that associate with the second component in the PCA, suggesting that they might share common environmental sources. Diet is the major route of exposure for all these metals, with the exception of Cd, where smoking prevails. A detailed questionnaire on diet habits was collected for all participants and further studies will address this topic. Several studies report a dramatic difference in serum/blood cadmium levels between smokers and non-smokers at a young age (3-fold increase), and a lower but still significant difference at older ages (approximately 2-fold increase) (44). This increase is confirmed in our study that shows 2-fold increase in Cd blood levels in smokers as compared to ex-or no-smokers. We observed that the association of smoking habits with OGG activity is greatly reduced and not significant when Cd levels are taken into account, suggesting a role for this metal in the mediation of the effects of smoke on OGG activity. [It is of note that both the blood Cd levels](#)

as well as OGG activity revert to normal in the category of the ex-smokers. This is in line with *in vitro* observations that, following acute exposure of human cells to Cd, excretion of the metal leads to **normalisation** of the redox cell status and restoration of an active OGG1 (11). OGG activity has been shown to be a predictive biomarker of lung cancer (45). In the study by Paz-Elizur et al. (45) a cumulative effect of low OGG activity and smoking was reported indicating that smoking increases the risk of mutation load (that may determine progress to cancer) not only via OGG1-mediated mechanisms. **Mouse and human cell lines lacking OGG1 show increased steady state levels of 8-oxoGua in their genome (46). Also cell lines that are not fully deprived of OGG1 but present decreased OGG1 activity due to partially inactivating polymorphisms (i.e. Ser326Cys) show slower repair of oxidatively-induced guanine modifications in vivo (47).** The reduction in OGG1 activity that we observe in our study in association with increased blood levels of some metals is unlikely to give rise to permanent alteration of the steady state level of 8-oxoGua but more likely to transitory changes associated with the persistence of the toxic metal.

Age-related decrease in both the NEAC and OGG activity were detected in our study indicating that the decline in the antioxidant capacity (48) together with that in the repair of oxidatively-induced DNA damage (19) may play an important role in age-related accumulation of cell damage by ROS.

Heritability estimates: the environmental factors prevail. The best-fitting biometric models indicated that environmental factors are the major contributors to inter-individual differences in metal levels (with some exceptions) as well as in NEAC and OGG activity.

Environmental exposures were also shown to govern the accumulation of metals, with some contribution by genetic factors, in a large adult twin population (36). In our study it is of note the contribution of genetic variance in the case of Mn and Zn which are all essential trace elements. It should be mentioned that in the case of Pb and Se significant shared

environmental influences were identified. Environmental effects shared within twin pairs reflect non heritable phenomena occurring during intrauterine life and/or the early postnatal period (e.g. maternal diet, gestational infections or chemical exposures during pregnancy). Pb passes the placenta and Pb-mediated epigenetic mechanisms in the foetus are dramatically associated with impaired brain development (49). Whether epigenetic mechanisms early in life might determine Pb body burden in adults should be investigated in larger studies.

The inter-individual differences in NEAC levels were mostly determined by the non-shared environmental component whereas the OGG capacity was accounted by both shared and non-shared environmental factors. This might account for the low within-pair correlations in MZ and DZ twin groups in the case of NAEC as compared to the high within-pair correlations in both zygosity groups in the case of OGG activity. In line with the idea of an environmental factors-driven antioxidant capacity, a study on elderly Danish twins (50) has shown that urinary markers of oxidative stress, measuring oxidatively-induced damage to nucleic acids and lipids, are predominantly determined by non genetic factors. Although epigenetic changes have been proposed in the link between oxidative stress levels and birth weight in twin neonates (51) and risk of complex diseases later in life (52) whether the shared environmental effects in the case of OGG activity are part of a “signature” by oxidative stress at birth on DNA repair capacity is presently very speculative.

The lack of genetic factors in determining DNA repair capacity was somewhat surprisingly. Previous studies have suggested that radiation-induced micronucleus frequency (reviewed in 53), mutagenic sensitivity to a variety of DNA damaging agents (54), and apoptotic (55) and cell-cycle (56) response to ionizing radiation are highly heritable. However, no effect of the genetic background was observed when baseline and radiation-induced DNA single strand breaks (SSB) were examined (57). [The human DNA repair proteome is susceptible to oxidation \(58\) and BER enzymes might be especially sensitive thus](#)

accounting for the environmental component when the repair of oxidised DNA bases or SSB is measured. In the study by Garm et al. (57) it was shown that SSB repair induced by γ -rays is accounted for by individual specific environmental exposures whereas the basal levels of endogenous SSB, γ -H2AX response and double strand break repair capacity can be accounted for by both common and non-shared environmental factors. Similarly, the shared environmental component prevails in the case of basal OGG activity. Birth is associated with a burst of oxidative stress (59) that might impact on the capacity to repair DNA damage later in life. Further studies are required to address this topic.

Conclusions

Genetic background may be critical for disease development, but environmental factors may have a dominant role in disease progression. This study provides clear evidence that it is the exposure to toxic elements in the environment that governs our capacity to respond to oxidative stress. Genetic factors play a minor role. Toxic metals, that may contaminate air, water, soil and food, are identified as important contributors via induction of oxidative stress. Our findings implicate that the prevention of adverse environments/life style habits is an effective measure to limit the deleterious health effects of excessive oxidatively-induced damage.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare they have no actual or potential competing financial interests.

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Table 1. Blood metal levels in twins as compared to reference values from Italian surveys conducted on healthy adult subjects

	This study		Reference values	
	Median (mean ^a)	5 th -95 th percentiles	Median (mean ^a)	5 th -95 th percentiles
Al	12.10 (13.25)	4.22-28.13	15.3 (17.0) ²	5.93-33.3
As	1.71 (2.34)	0.36-5.80	1.16 (1.14) ¹	0.28-5.32
Cd	0.60 (0.73)	0.23-1.70	0.52 (0.63) ¹	0.23-1.42
Co	0.10 (0.13)	0.03-0.34	0.14 (0.19) ¹	0.05-0.44
Cr	0.18 (0.39)	0.02-1.52	0.23 (0.38) ¹	0.06-1.09
Cu	919.0 (955)	739.7-1322.5	935 (938) ²	686-1157
Hg	1.72 (2.29)	0.36-6.80	1.15 (1.68) ¹	0.35-5.16
Mn	8.45 (8.69)	4.62-13.37	8.30 (8.74) ¹	4.41-14.5
Ni	0.52 (1.15)	0.10-4.56	0.90 (1.23) ¹	0.35-2.62
Pb	17.87 (23.58)	9.97-57.20	20.2 (24.0) ¹	7.38-51.7
Se	98.39 (102.24)	60.43-156.38	- (91.3) ³	-
Zn	5920.6 (6043)	4560.7-7940.3	6597 (6717) ²	5189-8337

Blood samples from 173 twins were analysed. Values are expressed as µg/L

^a arithmetic mean;

¹ Alimonti et al. (29); ² Alimonti et al. (60); ³ Alimonti et al. (30).

Table 2: Proportion of variability and contribution of metals to the five principal components (PC)

Statistical parameters	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5
Variance (%)	22	14	12	9	8
Cumulative Variance	0.22	0.36	0.48	0.57	0.65
Al	-0.002	0.531	0.0004	-0.091	-0.651
As	0.663	0.024	0.205	-0.254	0.293
Cd	0.406	0.397	0.008	-0.074	-0.357
Co	-0.121	0.572	-0.247	-0.513	0.356
Cr	-0.184	0.521	0.605	0.031	0.092
Cu	0.068	0.383	-0.461	0.573	0.254
Hg	0.636	-0.111	0.082	-0.402	0.122
Mn	0.233	0.448	-0.647	-0.057	0.059
Ni	0.036	0.515	0.568	0.295	0.231
Pb	0.689	0.004	0.070	-0.034	-0.158
Se	0.764	-0.101	-0.014	0.233	-0.015
Zn	0.696	-0.021	0.019	0.297	0.018

The numbers in the columns are factor loadings that represent the correlations between metals and principal components.

Table 3. Differences in metal blood levels by twin characteristics

	Al	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Hg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Se	Zn
Age at enrollment												
≤40	12.84	1.22	0.51	0.11	0.20	884.61	1.50	8.34	0.31	14.00	83.02	5334.79
>40	11.43	2.57	0.70	0.08	0.17	937.83	1.92	8.49	0.95	25.13	112.61	6617.55
		P<0.001	P<0.001	P=0.007		P=0.009	P=0.002		P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.001
Gender												
Male	11.45	2.62	0.53	0.08	0.18	867.95	1.78	7.30	0.71	25.04	109.16	6703.98
Female	12.35	1.37	0.69	0.12	0.19	955.35	1.66	8.66	0.46	15.72	94.98	5682.49
		P=0.003	P=0.001	P<0.001		P<0.001		P<0.001		P<0.001	P=0.004	P<0.001
Smoking habits												
Never–ex smokers	11.43	1.71	0.53	0.10	0.18	921.30	1.58	8.67	0.51	18.17	101.32	6020.75
Current smokers	13.39	1.80	0.89	0.12	0.18	902.09	1.92	7.56	0.55	17.88	92.79	5696.25
			P<0.001					P=0.009				
BMI												
<25	11.34	1.32	0.58	0.11	0.24	919.86	1.72	8.29	0.38	15.52	91.94	5614.26
≥25	12.11	2.55	0.63	0.10	0.15	918.68	1.69	8.47	0.84	23.39	105.94	6630.21
		P=0.001							P=0.002	P<0.001	P=0.002	P<0.001

The reported values are medians expressed as µg/L.

P values were obtained by Mann-Whitney U-test; only significant differences are reported.

Table 4. Association between NEAC or OGG activity and characteristics of twins

	NEAC						OGG activity					
	N	Mean \pm SD	β Coefficient	P	β Coefficient age adjusted	P _{adj}	N	Mean \pm SD	β Coefficient	P	β Coefficient age adjusted	P _{adj}
Age at enrollment												
≤ 40	50	2200.7 \pm 368.7					44	1.44 \pm 0.38				
>40	66	1814.7 \pm 333.0	-386.0	<0.01	-	-	62	1.21 \pm 0.38	-0.23	0.02	-	-
Gender												
Male	44	1982.8 \pm 427.2					44	1.30 \pm 0.37				
Female	72	1980.1 \pm 380.4	-2.72	0.98	-54.87	0.50	62	1.31 \pm 0.41	0.0005	1.0	-0.028	0.78
Smoking habits												
Never-ex smokers	87	1978.8 \pm 386.4					78	1.33 \pm 0.42				
Current smokers	27	1971.4 \pm 439.8	-12.97	0.89	-23.48	0.78	26	1.23 \pm 0.31	-0.11	0.05	-0.11	0.04
Zygoty												
MZ	84	1953.1 \pm 359.9					74	1.33 \pm 0.41				
DZ	32	2054.5 \pm 479.5	101.4	0.36	63.48	0.52	32	1.24 \pm 0.34	-0.09	0.39	-0.12	0.21
BMI												
<25	61	2025.4 \pm 388.2					55	1.31 \pm 0.43				
25-30	40	1942.2 \pm 414.4	-59.3	0.43	26.7	0.69	39	1.29 \pm 0.37	-0.03	0.62	-0.007	0.91
≥ 30	15	1904.4 \pm 388.1	-95.9	0.39	51.4	0.66	12	1.33 \pm 0.33	0.07	0.44	0.11	0.26

β coefficient is defined as the rate of change of the dependent variable (Y) for a unit change in the predictor variable (X). Age adjusted β coefficient is also displayed

SD=Standard Deviation; MZ: Monozygotic twins; DZ=Dizygotic twins; BMI= Body mass index (kg/m²)

Table 5. Regression coefficients, age adjusted, of metal blood levels and NEAC or OGG activity

	NEAC		OGG activity	
	β coefficient	P	β coefficient	P
Al	-3.28	0.57	-0.007	0.04
As	12.53	0.52	-0.012	0.26
Cd	-145.95	0.14	-0.162	0.009
Co	-620.9	0.06	-0.647	0.11
Cr	-5.80	0.94	0.002	0.98
Cu	-0.37	0.06	0.00002	0.93
Hg	4.56	0.73	-0.021	0.16
Mn	-19.92	0.07	-0.03	0.008
Ni	-19.53	0.43	-0.024	0.046
Pb	-6.95	0.03	0.003	0.21
Se	-0.48	0.72	0.0003	0.85
Zn	-0.02	0.63	0	0.85

Analysis for metal levels and NEAC or OGG activity were available on 103 and 96 twins respectively

Table 6. Standardized genetic and environmental variance components of NEAC, OGG activity and metal concentrations as estimated from the best-fitting structural equation models.

	Twins	Standardized variance components		
		A (95% CI)	C (95% CI)	E (95% CI)
NEAC	116	-	0.23 (0, 0.46)	0.77 (0.54, 1.00)
OGG activity	106	-	0.72 (0.57, 0.83)	0.28 (0.17, 0.43)
Al	170	0.17 (0, 0.39)	-	0.83 (0.61, 1.0)
As	170	0.15 (0, 0.39)	-	0.85 (0.61, 1.0)
Cd	170	0.36 (0.14, 0.55)	-	0.64 (0.45, 0.86)
Co	170	0.55 (0.32, 0.71)	-	0.45 (0.29, 0.68)
Cr	170	-	-	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Cu	170	0.21 (0, 0.41)	-	0.79 (0.59, 1.0)
Hg	170	0.33 (0.10, 0.53)	-	0.67 (0.47, 0.91)
Mn	170	0.69 (0.54, 0.79)	-	0.31 (0.21, 0.46)
Ni	170	0.32 (0.02, 0.56)	-	0.68 (0.44, 0.98)
Pb	170	-	0.44 (0.25, 0.59)	0.56 (0.41, 0.75)
Se	170	-	0.60 (0.45, 0.72)	0.40 (0.28, 0.55)
Zn	170	0.79 (0.67, 0.87)	-	0.21 (0.13, 0.33)

A, additive genetic variance; C, shared environmental variance; E, unique environmental variance. Covariates: age and gender. Numbers in parentheses indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Fig. 1

Figure 1: Distribution of NEAC and OGG activity in a subgroup of twins. A) NEAC was measured in plasma of 116 twins and is expressed as $\mu\text{moles/L}$ of reducing capacity. Mean: 1981 $\mu\text{moles/L}$; SD: 397 $\mu\text{moles/L}$; B) OGG activity was measured in lymphocytes of 106 twins and is expressed as fmoles of cleaved DNA substrate per μg of cell extracts. Mean: 1.3 fmoles/ μg ; SD: 0.4 fmoles/ μg .

Fig. 1 supplementary

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